

CONTRIBUTION OF COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE PROMOTION OF ISLAMIC FAITH IN POBLACION TALAYAN, MAGUINDANAO DEL SUR

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Contribution of Communication Technology in the Promotion of Islamic Faith in Poblacion Talayan, Maguindanao Del Sur

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Abstract

This study examines how communication technology promotes Islam in Barangay Poblacion, Talayan, Maguindanao del Sur. Due to the rapid growth of technology, Islamic groups and individuals have begun to use social media and mobile phones to spread Islam and engage with their communities. This research aimed to investigate the impact of new communication technologies on contemporary religious practices and beliefs. It explored how individuals utilize technology to access religious resources, connect with the global Muslim community, and participate in online religious activities. The study employed a quantitative methodology as a primary investigative approach. To achieve its objectives, a semi-structured questionnaire was used to explore how Muslim communities in Barangay Poblacion Talayan, Maguindanao del Sur, leverage technology to enhance their faith and strengthen community ties. The survey involved a total of fifty randomly selected individuals from Poblacion Talayan, Maguindanao. Among the respondents were Ulama, Asatidz, and members of the Bangsamoro Communication Network, all of whom reside in Talayan Maguindanao del Sur and are responsible for promoting the Islamic faith. Residents who were unfamiliar with Islam or unable to answer the questions were not included as respondents. Communication Technology Utilized in the Promotions of Islamic Faith results were based on statement indications, with some favoring “Yes” and others not. This suggests that not all communication technologies were used to promote Islam. In summary, respondents promoted Islam only via radio FM, Icom Radio, and cell phone. Challenges Confronted by Respondents in Promoting Islamic Faith Using Communication Technology showed that all statement indicator metrics preferred “Yes”. The absence of communication technology abilities makes promoting Islamic faith in Barangay Población Talayan become difficult.

Keywords: *communication technology, contributions, challenges, promotion, Islamic faith*

Introduction

In recent years, technology has become an essential component of our everyday lives, exerting an impact on various facets of society, including religious customs. The Islamic faith, characterized by its profound traditions and spiritual affiliations, has also experienced effects from technological progress. Technology has enabled Muslims to establish novel connections with their faith and community, through the utilization of Islamic applications, online resources, as well as virtual platforms for communal engagement and prayer. The convergence of technology and religion is a subject of escalating significance and curiosity, as scholars delve into the ways in which digital instruments can mold and enrich religious observances. Within the realm of the Islamic faith, the integration of technology has presented both prospects and obstacles.

Technology has facilitated access to Islamic knowledge for Muslims, enabling connections with scholars and fellow believers, as well as participation in religious rituals. Conversely, concerns have emerged regarding the potential erosion of traditional customs and the influence of digital distractions on spiritual development. Islam, boasting a following of over 1.8 billion individuals, stands as one of the world's rapidly expanding religions. Its teachings, practices, and doctrines derive from the Qur'an, the sacred scripture bestowed upon Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W) more than 1,400 years ago. In today's era of digitization, technology has opened up novel avenues for Muslims to explore and partake in Islamic teachings and practices. Ranging from virtual Quranic instruction to Islamic applications and websites, technology has streamlined the process for Muslims to strengthen their relationship with their faith and community.

Despite the numerous advantages that technology has brought to the cultivation of Islamic faith, there exist apprehensions regarding the influence of digital distractions and misinformation on religious rituals. This research endeavor is focused on investigating the impact of technology in nurturing Islamic faith, delving into both the advantageous and disadvantageous implications that technology imposes on the spiritual engagements of Muslims in contemporary society. Additionally, the realm of social media has emerged as a potent instrument for disseminating Islamic doctrines, establishing connections within the worldwide Muslim populace, and cultivating a sense of cohesion and camaraderie among adherents. The utilization of technology has also empowered Muslims to access resources related to halal dietary options, prayer schedules, and Islamic gatherings, thereby facilitating the observance of their faith in their day-to-day routines.

Nevertheless, in addition to these advantages, technology has prompted inquiries into its effects on the conventional observance of Islam. Certain commentators contend that the dependence on electronic resources could result in a superficial comprehension of the religion, creating a disconnect for followers from the profound spiritual and reflective aspects of Islamic customs. Furthermore, there are heightened concerns regarding the possibility of misinformation, cyberbullying, and other adverse impacts that may impede the welfare and spiritual development of individuals.

According to numerous scholars and ulama, it is believed that technology possesses the capacity to serve as a potent instrument for disseminating knowledge regarding Islam, facilitating connections among Muslims globally, and enhancing one's comprehension and observance of the faith. One of the most notable ways in which technology has fostered Islamic faith is by enhancing the accessibility of Islamic knowledge to a wider audience. Through digital platforms, adherents of Islam can avail themselves of a plethora of information concerning the religion, encompassing texts, discourses, and virtual educational sessions. This enables individuals to deepen their insight into the faith and engage with erudite figures and instructors hailing from diverse regions across the globe.

Many Ulama, Asatidz, and individuals in Talayan, Maguindanao Del Sur are facing challenges due to the emergence of new technology impacting the Islamic faith. The researcher is keen to explore the role of communication technology in promoting Islamic beliefs in Talayan, Maguindanao Del Sur. The findings of this research have the potential to shed light on the ways in which technology can be exploited to cultivate devotion to the Islamic faith in contemporary times. Individuals and groups of Muslims can benefit from this by gaining an understanding of how technology can be incorporated into their spiritual and religious rituals, which will ultimately strengthen their feeling of connection to their faith. In addition, this research has the potential to provide light on the opportunities and challenges that technology presents within the context of the Islamic faith, and it can also serve as a guide for the development of innovative solutions to solve these challenges.

In the end, this research has the potential to make a contribution to the enrichment of Islamic spirituality and to assist Muslims in navigating the digital age while maintaining their religious beliefs and practices. Last but not least, this could serve as a foundation for additional research or researchers who are relevant to this field in the future. It's possible that the articles will be used as supplementary references for their future efforts.

Research Questions

This study sought to examine the impact of technology on Islamic religion practices in Barangay Poblacion, Talayan, Maguindanao Del Sur. The objective was to enhance the spiritual connection and uphold Islamic traditions in the era of digital advancements.

1. What are the communication technology utilized in the promotions of Islamic faith?
2. How does communication technology contribute to the promotion of Islamic faith in Barangay Poblacion Talayan?
3. What are the challenges confronted by the respondents in promoting Islamic faith using communication technology?

Literature Review

Digital Resources Empower Learning

Individuals and communities all around the world have benefited greatly from the technological advancements that have been made in the field of Islamic faith. By utilizing a wide variety of digital platforms, applications, and online resources, technology has made it possible for Muslims to connect with their faith, have access to religious teaching, and participate in spiritual practices in ways that are both groundbreaking and inventive. Through an examination of the relevant literature and studies, this review will investigate the influence that technology has on the development of Islamic faith, focusing on the most important findings and insights from previous study conducted in this area.

The part that technology plays in fostering Islamic faith and spirituality among Muslims has been the subject of investigation in a number of studies. The usage of mobile applications for the purpose of reciting and memorizing the Quran among Muslim users was the subject of an investigation that was conducted by Al-Samarraie and Saeed (2018). Based on the findings of the study, mobile applications offered Muslims a convenient and easily available means of engaging with the Quran, which ultimately resulted in enhanced levels of religious knowledge and spiritual development respectively.

The influence of social media on religious practices among young Muslims was investigated in a different study that was conducted by Al-Rahmi and colleagues (2017). Based on the findings of the study, it was discovered that young Muslims utilized social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter in order to interact with persons who had similar beliefs, share content related to their religion, and take part in online conversations regarding Islamic doctrines. The participation in online activities helped to deepen their faith and sense of community, particularly in nations where Muslims do not constitute the majority population.

Islamic learning platforms that are accessible online have developed as a vital resource for the development of Islamic religion, in addition to mobile applications and social media. Using online courses to educate Islamic theology and jurisprudence was the subject of an investigation that was conducted by Khan (2019). According to the findings of the study, online learning platforms offered Muslims a multifaceted and participatory approach to enhancing their comprehension of Islamic concepts and practices, which ultimately resulted in an increase in religious literacy and faith.

Online Platforms Foster Community

Attempt to foster connections among Muslims all across the world. Individuals are able to engage in conversation, exchanging information, and seeking guidance on issues that are associated with the Islamic faith through the use of these platforms. Through the use of this online community, Muslims are able to feel a sense of solidarity and camaraderie with other people who share their beliefs,

regardless of where they are physically located.

One study that was carried out by Gary R. Bunt (2012) investigated the influence that technology has had on the Islamic faith, with a particular emphasis on using online platforms. According to the findings of the survey, internet platforms have developed into a great resource for Muslims who are interested in integrating themselves with other members of their faith community and gaining a deeper understanding of Islam. Individuals are able to gain access to religious teachings, participate in relevant conversations, and establish connections with religious leaders and scholars through the use of these platforms. According to the findings of the study, online platforms play a significant role in contributing to the development of Islamic faith and in fostering a sense of community among Muslims.

A study was carried out by Almourad and Alhumoud (2016) to investigate the impact that technology has on the propagation of the Islamic faith among younger generations. The research concluded that young Muslims' religious ideas and practices are significantly influenced by technology. This was found to be the case. A wealth of material about Islam, including holy books, education, and guidance, is now available to young people because of technological advancements. In addition, online platforms provide a venue for young Muslims to participate in conversations, meet with individuals in their religion community, and seek counsel from others. When it comes to encouraging young Muslims to actively participate in their faith, the study highlighted the significance that technology plays in developing a feeling of belonging and identity among young Muslims.

The influence of technology on Islamic education and learning was investigated. The findings of the study indicate that technological advancements have significantly altered the manner in which Muslims have access to religious education and information. For individuals who are interested in learning more about Islam, there is a multitude of materials available to them through internet platforms. These resources include online courses, lectures, and seminars. Individuals are now able to engage with religious texts and teachings in a manner that is both dynamic and immersive thanks to the advent of technology, which has made religious teaching more accessible and integrated. Within the context of the Islamic faith, the study brought to light the significance of technology in fostering personal development and learning that continues throughout one's life. The development of Islamic religion and the promotion of a sense of community among Muslims all over the world are both significantly aided by the proliferation of technology. Access to religious teachings, participation in conversations, the ability to connect with others in their faith community, and the opportunity to get a deeper understanding of Islam are all made possible through the use of online platforms. The way in which Muslims have access to Islamic education and information has been transformed by technology, which has made it more inclusive, participatory, and interesting to them. It is anticipated that technology will play an increasingly significant role in the promotion of the Islamic faith and in connecting Muslims all over the world as it continues to improve throughout the years.

Social media Connects Believers

There are millions of users all over the world who use social media platforms, and these platforms enable the exchange of information, ideas, and resources that are linked to the Islamic faith. Social media has become an essential component of people's everyday lives with millions of users. The development of a sense of community among Muslims, regardless of their physical location, can be facilitated by having this. By way of illustration, social media platforms such as Facebook and Instagram enable individuals to become members of groups or to follow pages that are devoted to Islamic teachings, events, and conversations. In recent years, for the benefit of researchers and academics. A significant shift has occurred in the manner in which individuals interact with their religious beliefs as a result of the proliferation of social media platforms. In this review, we will investigate the scientific literature and research that have been conducted on the topic of how technology, and more specifically social media, has impacted the way in which believers practice their Islamic faith.

A study that was conducted by Al-Badi and colleagues (2017) investigated the ways in which Muslims in Oman engage with their faith through the use of social media platforms. The researchers came to the conclusion that social media played a big part in the development of a sense of community among believers, since it offered a platform for the dissemination of religious content, and because it made it easier for people to have conversations about Islamic doctrines. It was reported by those who took part in the research that social media assisted them in maintaining a connection to their faith and gaining a deeper understanding of Islamic traditions.

In a comparable manner, Al-Rawi and Al-Qaysi (2019) conducted research to evaluate the influence that social media has on the religious practices of young Muslims in Iraq. According to the findings of the study, young Muslims make use of social media platforms like Facebook and Instagram in order to gain access to religious content, establish connections with religious leaders, and take part in online religious communities. The impact of social media on the dissemination of religious information and the promotion of Islamic principles among younger believers was another aspect that was addressed in the study.

It has also been discovered that social media can have an effect on the religious identity of believers, in addition to easing access to religious content and supporting the development of a sense of community. In 2018, Al-Zahrani conducted a study that investigated the impact that social media platforms have on the formation of the religious identity of Muslim women in Saudi Arabia. During the course of the study, the researcher discovered that social media platforms provided Muslim women with the opportunity to express their religious values, connect with individuals who had similar beliefs, and confront prejudices around Islam. Based on the findings of the study, it was determined that social media played a significant part in enabling Muslim women to declare their religious identity

in the world of digital technology.

There are several advantages that technology can bring to the process of cultivating Islamic religion; yet, there are also concerns that have been expressed by researchers regarding the potential adverse effects that social media could have on religious practice. In a study that was conducted in 2016, Al-Jenaibi investigated the difficulties that Muslims in the United Arab Emirates encounter when attempting to navigate the digital landscape while still adhering to their religious convictions. Despite the fact that social media platforms offered a means of connecting with other believers and gaining access to religious content, the researcher discovered that these platforms also brought concerns, such as the possibility of being exposed to unsuitable content and receiving incorrect information.

The literature and studies that are currently available shed light on the crucial role that technology, and more specifically social media, plays in the development of Islamic faith among faithful individuals. Through the use of social media platforms, Muslims have been given the opportunity to connect with their faith, have access to content that is religious, and participate in online religious communities. On the other hand, academics have also discovered the difficulties and dangers that are related with the utilization of technology inside of religious practices. It is necessary to conduct additional research in order to investigate the ways in which technology might be utilized to deepen the Islamic religion while also reducing the potential adverse effects.

E-book Islamic Knowledge

All aspects of our existence, including our religious practices, have been profoundly influenced by technology. Access to religious teachings and practices has become more simpler than it was in the past as a result of the proliferation of the internet, smartphones, and social media. Technology has been an essential factor in the development and propagation of the Islamic faith among adherents located all over the world. This is especially true in the case of Islam.

One of the most important ways in which technology has contributed to the improvement of Islamic faith is through the availability of resources on the internet. Muslims now have an easier time gaining access to religious teachings, interpretations of the Quran, and information about Islamic rituals because to the proliferation of resources such as websites, social media platforms, and mobile applications that are dedicated to Islamic knowledge. The purpose of these tools is not only to supply Muslims with useful knowledge, but also to facilitate connections between them and scholars and teachers who can assist them on their spiritual path.

The opportunity to communicate with other Muslims from all around the world is one of the ways that technology is helping to cultivate Islamic faith. The proliferation of social media platforms and online forums has made it possible for believers to interact with one another, discuss their experiences, pose questions to one another, and seek guidance from other Muslims. The feeling of belonging to a group and having a sense of camaraderie may be extremely uplifting and can also assist deepen one's faith.

Technology helps Muslims exercise their religion daily. Apps and websites assist Muslims track prayer hours, discover the Qibla, and listen to Quranic recitations. This is especially helpful for Muslims in non-Muslim majority nations with restricted mosque and Islamic resource access. Islamic education is easier for Muslims thanks to technology. Student can study from global scholars and teachers through online courses, webinars, and virtual classrooms without traveling far to traditional Islamic school. This accessibility has allowed more individuals, especially women and busy people, to study religion.

Despite these positives, technology may affect Islamic faith negatively. Critics say technology has made religion shallow, with people seeking rapid answers and bite-sized information rather than profound meditation and study. Muslims also worry about online misinformation and extremism.

Information Technology and its Role on Teaching the Qur'an

Allah Subhanahu Wata'ala (SWT) revealed the holy book known as the Qur'an to the Prophet Muhammad Sallallahu Alaihi Wa Sallam (SAW) through the angel Jibril that is also known as Gabriel. No one should act, say, or execute any activities unless they comply to the laws stated in the holy Qur'an. This is because the holy Qur'an is the complete guide for all beings in the universe, including those who are Muslims and those who consider themselves to be Muslims.

There are 114 chapters that make up the holy Qur'an, and in verse 2 of chapter 2, Allah declares the following about the Qur'an: "This is the Book, without any question (in its content), gives guidance to those who fear Allah." The second verse of Al-Baqrah. Currently, the Qur'an can be accessed on the internet through a variety of different channels. Not only did the number of people using the Internet throughout the world expand on a daily basis, but so did the number of people using the Qur'an by members of the Muslim ummah around the world.

According to Wikipedia (2015), over two billion people utilized the Internet. Many Muslims spend hours listing, remembering, learning, and investigating the Qur'an. According to Hosseini, Ramchahi, and Yusuf (2014), 44% of Internet users worldwide were Asian with 60% of them Muslim. India and Indonesia, with 204 million and 177 million Muslims, provided 140 million Internet users. China and Malaysia, with large Muslim populations, were among Asia's top 10 Internet users.

Islamic societies built websites to share knowledge among their ummah because of the Internet's impact on teaching, learning, and research. Thus, Qur'an, Arabic, and Hadith can be read online, and mobile versions are free to download on apps-store. The Qur'an can

also be recited online. Qur'an translations and interpretations are accessible in audio format for those who struggle with Arabic.

The Hadith from the Perspective of Contemporary ICT

The Prophet Muhammad's sayings, actions, and silent approval are called Hadith. Like the Qur'an, it was first collected and taught through reading. Thus, Muslim societies can now learn from Islamic Hadith schools like Sahih-Bukhari, Sahih-Muslim, Sunan Abu-Dawud, Malik, and their chain of transmitters via the Internet in multiple languages. By extension, the Hadith teaches people how to purify, absolve, connect well, and behave well. Such Hadith teachings have impacted Muslim society and relationships in numerous ways. Internet use has informed and adapted Islamic traditions to global challenges and changes, from neighborhood difficulties to political contests and prayer.

Thus, information technology has enlightened the Muslim world about global events and how to approach international relations and diplomacy, international politics, weather forecasts, health issues, etc.

The E-Learning and the Muslims Society

The rise of IT had transformed Muslim teaching and learning. IT creates strong learning environments and changes the learning and teaching process so students can learn in a practical, self-directed, and helpful way, according to Pulkkinen (2007). Elhadj, Aoun-Allah, Alsughayeir, and Alansari (2012) found that online Islamic classes and lectures taught the Qur'an and Tajweed. Reciting the Holy Qur'an is different from reading a standard Arabic text due to pronunciation requirements. Reciting the Qur'an properly is important for all Muslims and vital for prayers.

Since the Qur'an was revealed to the prophet (PBUH), teachers have taught students of all ages how to recite it. This method was the sole way to learn the Qur'an until the 20th century. Recent technology can capture the Qur'an's text and sound with Tajweed regulations. Listening to authentic Qur'anic recitations was feasible afterward.

Attending Islamic studies at home through virtual lectures is possible with IT. E-learning allowed Muslims to attend online classes and lectures by famous scholars worldwide. Computer applications helped beginners listen and understand text on the screen.

The IT and its Role on Islamic Software and Applications

Information Technology provides the availability of Qur'an and Hadith digitally through the medium of Islamic software such as in audio and text formats for mobile phones, iPods, and laptops. Islamic software is also accessible via the website for free and the installation on phones takes only seconds. Muslims living in non-Muslim countries, who find it difficult to have access to hard copies of the Qur'an or other Islamic literature, can use information technology to do so easily (Hosseini, Ramchahi, and Yusuf, 2014).

Islamic software for mobile phones, iPods, and PCs makes Qur'an and Hadith available digitally. The website offers free Islamic software that installs on phones in seconds. Information technology makes it easy for Muslims in non-Muslim nations to get hard copies of the Qur'an and other Islamic literature (Hosseini, Ramchahi, and Yusuf, 2014).

IT and the Question of Morality and Privacy from the Islamic Perspective Muslims can find a lot of information online. Whether for good or negative depends on user interest. Nobody owns the Internet, thus anyone can submit positive or negative information, objects, and images, making it unmanageable. The web contains all kinds of beneficial and negative information and objects.

Thus, using the internet to disseminate information and Islam is great, whereas pornography, gambling, and misappropriation are harmful. Internet users, especially Muslims ummah, must choose to use it properly, carefully, and intelligently. Our Holy Prophet Muhammad (Peace be upon him) advised Muslims to "purify your intention in all you do and fear Allah" (40th Hadith). Once you realize this, Allah will lead your internet searches. Allah gave us freedom and the right to choose good and evil is a test. Allah almighty says, "The human soul—the way he shaped it and inspired it with knowledge of its evil and good—bears witness to the truth that he who purifies it [of all impiety] will succeed while he who corrupts it will fail." Additionally, privacy in today's world Technology has become a nightmare where third parties steal data, information, and communication over the internet, wifi, or other means without consent. This breach of privacy through technology allows others to hear, read, and edit messages. Electronically listening to human conversations without authorization is illegal. A third party can tap and change any internet, wireless, or other communication between two people. Allah (SWT) addresses this in An-Nur (27).

Methodology

Research Design

The study used quantitative method approach intended as a key method of investigation in this study. In order to answer the objectives of this study, a survey in Barangay Poblacion Talayan Maguindanao del Sur was conducted using a semi-structured questionnaire. The purpose of this survey was to collect the necessary information on the contribution of technology in the Muslim community regarding the use of technology supporting Islamic faith and the growth of the community. After the respondents complied with the necessary answers regarding their current status in terms of propagation on Islamic faith, the responses were evaluated. By conducting a survey question, which was included in the data of the study, it was possible to determine the extent to which the community's technological

advancements contributed to the development of the Islamic faith.

Respondents

It involved a total of fifty individuals randomly selected lived in Poblacion Talayan Maguindanao who were selected to take part in the survey as respondents of the study. Respondents who are included in the process of collecting data of the study were the Ulama, Asatidz, and the member of the Bangsamoro Communication Network resided in Talayan Maguindanao del Sur who are task to broadcast Islamic faith. Residents who do not know about Islam and incapable of answering the questions were not included as a respondent. These individuals were carefully selected to serve as respondents for the survey, ensuring a diverse representation of the community. Their insights and experiences were invaluable in providing a comprehensive understanding of the topic under investigation. The selection process aimed to include various demographics, allowing for a well-rounded analysis of the perspectives within the local population.

Instrument

In the course of this investigation, an Interview guide questionnaire served as the research instrument. Additionally, the document analysis technique was utilized in the process of conducting interviews with the respondents in order to determine the impact that technology has had on the Muslim community of Barangay Poblacion, Talayan in terms of the techniques of nurturing Islamic faith and the engagements of the Muslim community. For the purpose of gathering information regarding their own personal experiences and observations, these methods are also utilized. For the purpose of determining who of the responses were qualified, the guide questions were prepared. In addition, respondents were allowed to freely express their own opinions and experiences, and they were encouraged to speak the Maguindanaon dialect so that they could quickly and readily communicate their thoughts. Additionally, interviews were recorded to guarantee that the results were reliable.

Data Analysis

The data collected in this study were systematically organized and analyzed based on the respondents' answers to the questionnaire. To quantify the frequency of occurrence for each variable, both relative frequency and percentage were employed. This approach allowed for a clearer understanding of trends and patterns within the data. The analysis aimed to highlight significant findings, providing insights that could inform further research and contribute to a deeper understanding of the community's perspectives. By meticulously categorizing and interpreting the responses, the study ensured that the results were both meaningful and actionable.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to strict ethical standards, ensuring the privacy and rights of all participants were upheld. To protect their identities, all data was de-identified and anonymized, thereby minimizing any potential risks associated with participation. Additionally, informed consent was obtained from each participant, clearly outlining the purpose of the study and their rights. This commitment to ethical practices not only fosters trust between researchers and participants but also enhances the integrity of the research process, ensuring that the findings are both credible and respectful of individual privacy.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of the findings gathered from the respondent of the resident in Barangay Poblacion, Talayan, Maguindanao del Sur.

Profile of the Respondent

Table 1. *Frequency Distribution of the Respondents by Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
21-29 Years Old	15	30%
30-39 Years Old	20	40%
40-52 Years Old Or Above	15	30%
Total	50	100%

The age distribution of study participants is shown in the table above. The list above shows respondents' ages: 21–29, 30–39, and 40+. In the table aforementioned, most responses were 30–39 years old. It found that 30% of respondents were 21–29 years old and 40% were 40 or older. Of these 40% are 30–39 years old, 30% are 21–29, and 30% are 40 or older. Data showed that most responders were 30–39 years old.

Table 2. *Frequency Distribution of the Respondents by Educational Level*

<i>Educational Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
High School	20	40%
Senior High School 12	5	10%
College	25	50%
Total	50	100%

The demographic profile of this study's respondents, including their educational level, is shown in the table above. According to the table above, respondents were high school, senior high school, and college graduates. In the table above, most responders were well educated or university graduates. 50% of 50 those who responded have a college degree, 40% are high school graduates, and 10% are senior high school grads. Many responders were in educational bracket 25.

Table 3. *Frequency Distribution of the Respondents by Occupation*

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Madrassa Teacher	10	20%
Kagawad - (Government Employees)	3	6%
Rhotalayan - (Government Employees)	2	4%
Farmer - (Self Employed)	30	60%
Tailor - (Self Employed)	3	6%
Driver - (Self Employed)	2	4%
Total	50	100%

The table above shows the demographic profile of this study's respondents, specifically their occupation. As seen in the table, respondents worked as Madrassa teachers, kagawads, RHU Talayan, farmers, tailors, and drivers. The table above reveals that most responders were farmers. Thus, 60% of the participants (30 out of 50) reported farming as a reliable livelihood, 20% were Madrassa Teachers (10 out of 50), and the remaining small groups varied from 3 to 2 respondents each: kagawads, Talayan rural health unit employee, tailor, or driver. If combined, these minor groups will make up 20% of the study's responses. According to the data, most respondents were farmers.

Table 4. *Frequency Distribution of the Respondents by Income*

Income	Frequency	Percentage
2,000 Monthly	12	24%
3,000 Monthly	5	10%
1,500 Monthly	30	60%
9,000 Monthly	3	6%
Total	50	100%

The demographic profile of this study's respondents, including income, is shown in the table above. This table shows the earnings of respondents in the following ranges: 2k, 3k, 1,500k, or 9k each month. The following data reveals that most responders earned Ph 1,500.00 each month. Of the 50 responders, 60% earned 1,500.00, 24% earned 2,000.00, 10% earned 3,000.00, and 6% earned 9,000.00. Most responders earned \$1,500 or less.

Table 5. *Communication Technology Utilized in the Promotions of Islamic Faith*

Statement Indicator	Frequency				Total
	YES	Percentage	NO	Percentage	
Do you use Radio FM for promoting Islamic faith.	42	84%	8	16%	50 OR 100%
Do you use mobile Phone for promoting Islamic faith.	47	94%	3	6%	50 OR 100%
Do you use Icom for promoting Islamic faith.	35	70%	15	30%	50 OR 100%
Do you use Laptop for promoting Islamic faith.	20	40%	30	60%	50 OR 100%
Do you use online method for promoting Islamic faith.	5	10%	45	90%	50 OR 100%
Do you use webinars for promoting Islamic faith.	4	8%	46	92%	50 OR 100%
Do you use Google meet for promoting Islamic faith.	2	4%	48	96%	50 OR 100%
Do you use advertisements for promoting Islamic faith.	15	30%	35	70%	50 OR 100%

The above table exhibits frequency and percentage of statement indicators about Islamic faith promotion communication technology. These statements indicate this study's section: The use of Radio FM, mobile phones, Icom, laptops, online methods, webinars, Google meet, and advertisements to promote Islamic faith.

With their respective percentages, the table reveals that all metrics based on the statement indicators supported the remark or description of "Yes". FM radio with 42 or 84%, With 94% or 47/50 responders using mobile. Either 35 or 70% Icom usage. Radio FM, Icon, and mobile phones were utilized by most responders to promote Islam.

Those who preferred "NO" are revealed. Virtual events for promoting Islamic faith via laptop with 60% or 20 out of 50 respondents, online forums with 90% or 45 out of 50 respondents, online courses with 90% or 45 out of 50 respondents, webinars with 92% or 46 out of 50 respondents, and google meet. This result would mean that the communication technology regularly used by the respondents in promoting Islamic faith were FM radio, mobile phone, Icom radio.

Furthermore, the responders solely promoted Islam via radio FM, Icom, and cell phone. These findings were supported by the investigation that was conducted by Al-Samarraie and Saeed (2018). Based on the findings of the study, mobile applications offered Muslims a convenient and easily available means of engaging with the Quran, which ultimately resulted in enhanced levels of religious knowledge and spiritual development respectively.

Communication Technology Contribute to the Promotion of Islamic Faith

Table 6. *Frequency Distribution of the respondents by Communication Technology Contribute to the Promotion of Islamic Faith*

Statement Indicator	Frequency				Total
	YES	Percentage	NO	Percentage	
Do you use social media platforms to learn about Islamic teaching.	10	20%	40	80%	50 OR 100%
Do you follow any Islamic influencers on social media.	45	90%	5	10%	50 OR 100%
Do you think communication technology has helped in spreading Islamic teaching in Barangay Poblacion Talayan.	38	76%	12	24%	50 OR 100%
Have you shared Islamic content on your social media accounts.	4	8%	46	92%	50 OR 100%
Do you think Islamic organization in Barangay Poblacion Talayan effectively utilize communication technology for promotion.	45	90%	5	10%	50 OR 100%
Do you think communication technology can help in bridging the gap between different Islamic communities in Barangay Poblacion Talayan.	41	82%	9	18%	50 OR 100%
Have you participated in any online Islamic discussions.	10	20%	40	80%	50 OR 100%
Do you think online Islamic classes are beneficial for the community.	15	30%	35	70%	50 OR 100%

The table above provides frequency and proportion of statement indicators on how communication technology promotes Islamic faith in this study's geography. This section's statement indicators: 1. Are you an Islamic education social media user. 2. Do you follow Islamic social media influencers. 3. Do you think communication technology has propagated Islam in Barangay Poblacion Talayan. 4. Post Islamic stuff on social media. 5. How well do Barangay Poblacion Talayan Islamic organizations promote themselves with communication technology? 6. Do you think technology can help Barangay Poblacion Talayan's Islamic community communicate? 7. Do you participate in Islamic online discussions. 8. Are online Islamic classes community-beneficial?

The following table demonstrates that all metrics based on the statement indicators favored the remark or description of "Yes" with their corresponding percentage: 2. Are you following any Islamic influencers on social media? 90% or 45/50 replies. 3. Have communication technologies propagated Islamic teaching in Barangay Poblacion Talayan? 66% (33 out of 50) think so. 5. Do Islamic organizations in Barangay Poblacion Talayan effectively use communication technology for promotion? 90% or 45 out of 50 responded. 6. Do you think communication technology can help Islamic communities in Barangay Poblacion Talayan get along? 82% (41 of 50) think so. This showed that following Islamic influencers on social media, communication technologies, and bridging the gap between Islamic groups promotes Islamic faith. This findings suggest that majority of the respondents followed the Islamic influencers on social media, therefore, communication technologies propagated Islamic teaching in Barangay Poblacion Talayan, it help Islamic communities and bridging the gap between Islamic groups.

Furthermore, the influence of social media on religious practices among young Muslims was investigated in a different study that was conducted by Al-Rahmi and colleagues (2017). Based on the findings of the study, it was discovered that young Muslims utilized social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter in order to interact with persons who had similar beliefs, share content related to their religion, and take part in online conversations regarding Islamic doctrines. The participation in online activities helped to deepen their faith and sense of community, particularly in nations where Muslims do not constitute the majority population.

In contrast, the table reveals that all measurements based on the statement indicators favored the comment or description of "No" as shown in the following percentage. Use social media platforms to learn about Islamic teaching, 92% or 46 out of 50 respondents, participate in online Islamic discussions, and 7 out of 50 respondents think online Islamic classes are good for the community. This section was negative because most respondents were farmers and couldn't use this kind of platforms. This finding is contrary to the investigation that was conducted by Khan (2019). According to the findings of the study, online learning platforms offered Muslims a multifaceted and participatory approach to enhancing their comprehension of Islamic concepts and practices, which ultimately resulted in an increase in religious literacy and faith.

Challenges Confronted by the Respondents in Promoting Islamic Faith Using Communication Technology

The above table illustrates the frequency and proportion of statement indicators about the respondents' obstacles in promoting Islamic faith via communication technology in this study's location. Statement indicators for this study section: 1. Do communication technology difficulties hinder Islamic religion promotion. 2. Does lack of technology skills hinder Islamic religion promotion? 3. Does misinformation and unfavorable stereotypes affect Islamic religion promotion through communication technology? 4. Do you struggle to preach Islam to young people using technology? 5. Do you think lack of resources hinders Islamic religion promotion through communication technologies. 6. Do you struggle to use new communication technology to promote Islam.

All statement indicator-based measures supported the remark or description of "Yes" as shown in the table below with their respective percentages: 1. 60% or 30 out of 50 respondents experience difficulties spreading Islamic faith via communication technology. 2. Would you say lack of technological skills hinders Islamic religion promotion? 90% or 45 out of 50 respondents said yes. 3. To promote Islamic faith through communication technology, 78% (39 out of 50) think disinformation and unfavorable stereotypes do. 4. Do 82%

or 41 out of 50 respondents feel it difficult to engage younger generations with communication technologies to promote Islamic faith? 5. 70% of respondents (35 out of 50) say lack of resources is a challenge in promoting Islamic faith using communication technologies. 6. 86% or 43 out of 50 responders struggle to adapt to modern communication technology for spreading Islamic faith. The second statement indication had the highest frequency and equivalent percentage, whereas the sixth had the second. As for frequency and proportion, statement indication number one ranks lowest.

Table 7. *Frequency Distribution of the Respondents by Challenges Confronted by the Respondents in Promoting Islamic Faith Using Communication Technology*

Statement Indicator	Frequency				Total
	YES	Percentage	NO	Percentage	
Do you face challenges in promoting Islamic faith using communication technology.	30	60%	20	40%	50 OR 100%
Do you think lack of technological skills is a challenges in promoting Islamic faith.	45	90%	5	10%	50 OR 100%
Do you think misinformation and negative stereotypes impact the promotion of Islamic faith through communication technology.	39	78%	11	22%	50 OR 100%
Do you find it challenging to engage with younger generations through communication technology to promote Islamic faith.	41	82%	9	18%	50 OR 100%
Do you believe lack of resources is a challenge in promoting Islamic faith through communication technology.	35	70%	15	30%	50 OR 100%
Do you encounter difficulties in adapting to new communication technology for promoting Islamic faith.	43	86%	7	14%	50 OR 100%

Despite this, the table showed that all metrics based on statement indicators suggested “Yes”. This implied that lack of communication technology and abilities makes promoting Islamic faith in Barangay Poblacion Talayan difficult.

This study examined how online platforms, mobile apps, and social media affect Islamic practice and comprehension in Barangay Poblacion Talayan, Maguindanao. Technology was used to access religious resources, communicate with the global Muslim community, and participate in virtual religious events. Surveys, interviews, and observations were used to gather community and religious leader insights.

This study examined how technology affects Islamic faith in Barangay Poblacion Talayan, Maguindanao, and may not apply to other communities. Research was limited by internet availability, technological literacy, and cultural variables that could affect religious technology use and reception. The study's time and resources may have limited data gathering and analysis.

This study used descriptive-quantitative and qualitative methods. To answer this study's objectives, a structured questionnaire or interview guide questionnaire was used to gather information on how technology influences Muslim communities' use of technology to nurture Islamic faith and grow community in Barangay Poblacion Talayan, Maguindanao del Sur.

This study used an interview guide questionnaire. Document Analysis Technique was used to interview respondents to determine how technology affects the Barangay Poblacion Talayan Muslim community's nurturing of Islamic faith and engagement. These strategies also acquire personal observation and experience data. Guide questions were created to identify qualified respondents. Interviews were taped to assure dependability, and respondents were free to voice their opinions and experiences in Maguindanao. For the respondents' profiles, according to the survey. The bulk of responders were 30 to 39 years old, had a 25-year education, were farmers, and earned 1,500.

Communication Technology Utilized in the Promotions of Islamic Faith results were based on statement indications, with some favoring “Yes” and others not. This suggests that not all communication technologies were used to promote Islam.

In summary, respondents promoted Islam only via radio FM, Icom, and cell phone. Challenges Confronted by Respondents in Promoting Islamic Faith Using Communication Technology showed that all statement indicator metrics preferred “Yes”. The absence of communication technology abilities makes promoting Islamic faith in Barangay Población Talayan difficult.

Conclusions

The study found that Communication Technology Utilized in the Promotions of Islamic Faith, some favored the remark or description of “Yes” and some did not. This suggests that not all communication technologies were used to promote Islam. In summary, respondents promoted Islam only via radio FM, Icom, and cell phone.

Furthermore, the study found out that majority of the respondents followed the Islamic influencers on social media, therefore, communication technologies propagated Islamic teaching in Barangay Poblacion Talayan, it help Islamic communities and bridging the gap between Islamic groups.

Thus, the study concludes that respondents' obstacles in promoting Islamic faith utilizing communication technology in this study's location are lack of abilities in using new technology. Thus, the absence of communication technology abilities makes promoting

Islamic faith in Barangay Poblacion Talayan difficult.

Based on the conclusion of the study provided the basis for the following recommendations, which are strongly recommended.

It was proposed by the researcher that future researchers carry out an in-depth and additional investigation about the utilization of communication technology in formal settings such as schools and traditional Madrasas, as well as the effectiveness of these technologies, particularly with regard to the religious components of the matter.

It is strongly recommended by the researcher that a study of a similar nature be carried out in order to encompass higher and more formal platforms or institutions, such as colleges and universities.

It is possible that the similar studies that have not yet been carried out will concentrate on elements that are different from those that have been researched or discussed in this study. It is possible that it is not restricted to a single religious tradition.

It is strongly recommended by the researcher that studies be carried out that highlight the fulfilling work that our Asatidz do in terms of teaching. This will ensure that they are more recognized and given more prominence because of their contributions. In addition, this is done so that we can have an understanding of the obstacles that our religious workers face on a daily basis in order to accomplish their missions.

It is recommended by the researcher that studies about the governmentalization of independent Madrasas in the country be carried out, or at the very least, the prospects of its actualization. Moreover, to incorporate religious organizations that are capable of providing an appropriate route for the study of a particular religious faith.

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